

IPBES Transformative Change Assessment Chapter 5. Data Management Report 5.3 Analysis of civil society initiatives

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Description

This report corresponds to the IPBES transformative change assessment. The scoping report of the assessment describes that one of the aims is to identify actions to bring about change by a wide variety of actors. As part of the chapter's mandate to prepare a synthesis and assessment of sets of actions enabling and encouraging transformative change at all scales for a sustainable world, section 5.4.4 assesses two sets of actions by civil society: rural social innovations and environmental justice movements.

Process overview

Protocol

1. Rural social innovations across Europe

Type of analysis/search/review: Systematic literature review of empirical case studies on rural social innovations across Europe, between 2000 and 2024.

Search languages: English and Spanish

Search engine: Scopus

Exact date of search: 27 September 2023

Search terms:

TITLE-ABS-KEY (transformation) OR (social AND innovation) OR (grassroots AND innovation) OR (transitions) OR (social AND entrepreneurship)

AND

TITLE-ABS-KEY (rural)

AND

TITLE-ABS-KEY (Austria OR Belgium OR Bulgaria OR Croatia OR Cyprus OR Czech Republic OR Denmark OR Estonia OR Finland OR France OR Germany OR Greece OR Hungary OR Ireland OR Italy OR Latvia OR Lithuania OR Luxembourg OR Malta OR Netherlands OR Poland OR Portugal OR Romania OR Slovakia OR Slovenia OR Spain OR Sweden OR "United Kingdom" OR Europe) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (project OR case).

AND

(EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "MEDI") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "COMP") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "MATH") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "BIOC") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "NURS") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "PSYC") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "CHEM") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "CENG") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "MATE") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "NEUR") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "PHYS") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "PHAR") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "IMMU") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "DENT"))

AND

PUBYEAR > 1999 AND PUBYEAR < 2024

AND

LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ar") AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English") OR LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "Spanish")).

Sample extracted: 57 academic articles (including a total of 100 cases of rural social innovations as some articles described several cases).

Location and format of the data (A): IPBES_TCA_DMR5.3_rural social innovations_(A).csv

Fields extracted:

- Publication Type
- Authors
- Author Full Names
- Article Title
- Source Title
- Abstract
- ISSN
- eISSN
- ISBN
- Journal Abbreviation
- Journal ISO Abbreviation
- Publication Date
- Publication Year
- Volume
- Issue
- Start Page
- End Page
- Article Number
- DOI
- DOI Link

Treatment applied: Using information from the articles, case studies of rural social innovations were categorized by the following elements: sectors (including agrifood, tourism, forestry, or energy), scale of action (local, subnational and national), main focus (environmental, social, both), main problematic (depletion of natural resources, soil contamination or degradation, climate change, land loss, unsustainable practices), and nature of interventions (creation of associations, network development, resources management). These elements were used to carry out descriptive statistical analyses.

2. Environmental justice movements

Type of analysis/search/review: Analysis of the Environmental Justice Atlas

Search engine: Environmental Justice Atlas (Scheidel et al., 2020; Scheidel et al., 2023; Temper et al., 2015; online database: <https://ejatlas.org/>)

Exact date of data retrieval: 5 July 2023

Treatment applied: This worldwide database includes 3,731 cases of environmental conflicts documented and occurring since 1992. 2802 cases were selected for further analysis. Were excluded:

- Cases that started before 1992
- Cases documenting mobilizations that primary unfold at national and international scale, not linked to a specific case
- Cases with insufficient documentation
- Inconclusive cases, that did not report any outcome yet
- Cases reporting only one outcome

Selection of additional empirical and conceptual articles known by the authors to be relevant for the topic or recommended by reviewers during external review of the chapter have been used for the analyses of the environmental justice movement cases. Across cases, the focus of the movement, the type of mobilization (non-violent form of persuasion, non-cooperation, non-violent intervention and disruptive intervention), its outcome and its timeline were described in order to assess the transformative potential of these movements.

Location of the data: For further information about the dataset, please visit the Environmental Justice Atlas: <https://ejatlas.org/>

3. Figure 5.9

Figure caption: Spatial distribution of priority areas for species and environmental social movements - The background map displays priority areas for over 180 000 terrestrial vertebrate and plant species globally (Jung et al 2021). Geometric shapes show the location of environmental social movements in defense of their environment (n= 2,802) for which the outcome was violence against the movement (squares), reform of the activity (circles), or suppression of the activity (triangles).

Data provenance: Environmental Justice Atlas and UN Biodiversity Map

Exact date of data retrieval: 20 April 2024

Treatment applied: Two different datasets were combined to understand the relationships between environmental mobilizations and the local conditions of biodiversity. The 2802 environmental justice movements cases selected from the environmental justice atlas in the previous set of analyses were used for social mobilization in defense of nature. These cases were plotted according to the reaction they triggered.

The dataset corresponding to the areas of global importance for biodiversity conservation, carbon storage and water provision from the maps of the UN Biodiversity Lab were retrieved to report on the local condition of biodiversity (Jung et al, 2021a). Using the areas of global importance for terrestrial biodiversity, the fractions of protected areas (World Database on Protected Areas, 2019) were locked in as baseline (Jung et al 2021b). Priority areas ranked by the most (1-10%) to least (90-100%) important areas to conserve globally were binned in 6 classes representing 'Very High' to 'Very Low' priority. The map is plotted at 10/50 km resolution in Robinson projection.

Location and format of the data: Repository of the data process and scripts:
https://github.com/IPBES-Data/IPBES_TCA_ch5_ejatlaz

Definitions of files

ID	Names	File Type	Size	Description
A	1_IPBES_TCA_DMR 5.3_rural initiatives articles_(A).csv	csv	14 KB	57 academic articles describing rural initiatives cases across Europe

References

Jung, M., Arnell, A., De Lamo, X., Garcia-Rangel, S., Lewis, M., Mark, J., Merow, C. et al. 2021a. Areas of global importance for terrestrial biodiversity, carbon, and water. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*.

Jung, M., Arnell, A., De Lamo, X., García-Rangelm, S., Lewis, M., Mark, J., Merow, C., Miles, L., Ondo, I., Pironon, S., Ravilious, C., Rivers, M., Schepashenko, D., Tallowin, O., van Soesbergen, A., Govaerts, R., Boyle, B. L., Enquist, B. J., Feng, X., ... Visconti, P. 202b1. Areas of global importance for conserving terrestrial biodiversity, carbon, and water (1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5006332>.

Scheidel, A., D. Del Bene, Juan Liu, G. Navas, S. Mingorría, F. Demaria, S. Avila, Brototi Roy, I. Ertör, L. Temper, J. Martínez-Alier 2020. Environmental conflicts and defenders: A global overview. *Global Environmental Change*, 63. 102104.

Scheidel, A., Fernández-Llamazares A., Helen Bara A., Del Bene D., David-Chavez D. M., Fanari E., Garba I., Hanaček K., Liu J., Martínez-Alier J., Navas G., Reyes-García V., Roy B., Temper L., Thiri M. A., Tran D, Walter M., Whyte K.P.. 2023. Global impacts of extractive and industrial development projects on Indigenous Peoples' lifeways, lands, and rights. *Science Advances*.

Temper, L., D. Del Bene, J Martínez-Alier, 2015. Mapping the frontiers and front lines of global environmental justice. *J. of Political Ecology* 22 (1), 255-278.